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AN EXPLORATION OF THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF COLLEGE STUDENTS UTILIZING POWER NAP FOR ACADEMIC MOTIVATION

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ABSTRACT

The qualitative study explored the lived experiences of college students of Abuyog Community College regarding the effects of power naps on academic motivation. Grounded in the Restorative Theory of Sleep and Self-Determination Theory, the research used a hermeneutic phenomenological approach through semi-structured interviews of eight college students. Thematic analysis revealed two main themes: Power Nap as a Source of Rejuvenation and Enduring Academic Exhaustion, with sub-themes reflecting mental and physical exhaustion, self-control against napping, and setting into fatigue. In conclusion, participants emphasized the restorative benefits of power naps in academic productivity. However, some resisted napping due to time constraints, fear of oversleeping, or personal preference. Findings suggest that integrating short rest periods may enhance students' academic well-being and performance. Moreover, the paper contributes to the limited localized research on sleep practices and calls for institutional support in promoting balanced, rest-conscious academic environments for student success.

Keywords: *power nap, academic motivation, lived experiences, academic exhaustion, thematic analysis*

INTRODUCTION

Sleep is a biologically unique, controlled, and active state that is vital to health and well-being (Carley & Farabi, 2016). It is considered as a natural biological process that enables the brain and the body to rest, recover, and function properly (Cleveland Clinic, 2023). In the study by Crivello & Barsocchii (2019), getting quality sleep is closely linked to improved physical health, mental clarity, and emotional stability.

Adults, on average, require approximately eight hours of sleep each night to maintain optimal functioning (Okano et al., 2019). In general, most healthy adults need at least seven hours of sleep per night to support overall well-being. However, regularly getting less than the recommended amount of sleep is linked to an increased risk of various health issues, including weight gain, diabetes, hypertension, heart disease, stroke, and depression. Furthermore, it is not only the quantity of sleep that matters but also its quality, as disrupted or poor-quality sleep can significantly impact both physical and mental health. Chronic sleep deprivation not only impairs cognitive function and mental well-being but also has long-term consequences for physiological health. Thus, it is essential to examine the impact of sleep on the human body and explore potential solutions to the growing issue of sleep deprivation.

Associated with sleep is the power nap, which is a brief, intentional rest designed to reduce fatigue and restore a person's alertness (Summer, 2023). Power naps usually last for 10 to 15 minutes

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with benefits to a person's cognitive function and performance (George et al., 2024). This is especially true for college students who are under significant stress from their degree programs, which frequently causes them to sacrifice sleep in order to give more time to studying. Consequently, research indicates that as many as 60% of college students experience poor sleep quality (Schlarb et al., 2017).

The results of the study by Hershner and Chervin (2014) indicated that college students who do not get enough sleep have lower GPAs, have difficulty learning, and are more prone to mental health issues. Similarly, according to Pilcher and Walters (1997), students who were sleep deprived for 24 hours did poorly on cognitive tasks and were unaware of their diminished abilities. Conversely, Okano et al. (2019) discovered that students who adhered to regular sleep schedules performed better academically.

Several numbers of research about sleep have been done in lab settings, which interferes with the participants' normal sleep cycles. Moreover, a lot of research about sleep has mainly focused on its cognitive outcomes, such as memory and attention, ignoring the effects of power naps on students' emotional and psychological health, which are equally important for learning. This gap in the literature motivated the researchers to conduct a study exploring the lived experiences of students who utilize power naps as a means of academic motivation.

Additionally, while previous research focused on the cognitive benefits of sleep, the effect of power naps on students' motivation and sustained focus during studying were not extensively studied. Understanding this relationship could have enhanced knowledge of how naps influenced mental readiness, learning engagement, and memory retention.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aimed to explore the lived experiences of college students who utilized power naps to boost their drive or desire to be more engaged with their studies and strive for success in their academic pursuits.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the lived experience of college students having power naps?
2. How does power naps influence participants' academic motivation?
3. How does not taking power naps affect the academic motivation among students?
4. What specific challenges did college students face that prevented them from taking power naps?
5. How did researchers reflect on their study of power naps?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design This study used a hermeneutic phenomenological approach to understand college students' experiences with power naps and how these naps helped improve their focus and motivation in academics. This qualitative method allowed researchers to explore how students viewed and integrated power naps into their study to improve academic performance.

Research Instrument This study utilized semi-structured interviews as the main data collection method. Interviews were conducted by designated interviewers who adhered to a predetermined question guide to obtain comprehensive insights into participants' experiences with power naps.

Validation of Research Instrument To ensure the instrument's face validity were developed based on their relevance to the research objectives. Moreover, the research adviser reviewed the research instruments to check if the interview questions were appropriate and acceptable for investigating students' power nap experiences.

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Locale of the Study The research was conducted at Abuyog Community College (ACC), Abuyog, Leyte. The researchers opted to choose this institution because they are students of the said school. This made reaching out to participants become easier and more practical.

Research Participants To ensure the collection of rich and comprehensive data, participants were chosen through a snowball purposive sampling from various college departments. A total of eight students volunteers were chosen— 4 males and four females—to ensure equal gender representation and to gather in-depth insights. The participants met the following criteria: Students who regularly engaged in power napping, and students who did not engage in power napping.

This sampling method also allowed the researchers to compare the perspectives of male and female students regarding the perceived benefits of power naps in terms of academic motivation, concentration, and achievement.

Data Analysis Thematic analysis was used to examine the data. In this approach, the interview transcripts were carefully reviewed and reread to identify key responses, derive meaning, organize those meaning into categories, and develop overarching themes that captured the participants' shared experiences. This study was well-suited for thematic analysis, as it allowed the researchers to interpret and classify the qualitative data based on recurring patterns, providing a comprehensive understanding of how power naps relate to students' academic motivation and mental focus.

Data Gathering Procedure The researchers asked permission from the College President before beginning the interviews with the selected participants. On the day of the interviews, each participant signed an informed consent form prior to the data collection. This ensured that their participation was entirely voluntary and that they had been fully informed about the study's purpose, goals, and their rights as participants. Each interview was conducted in a respectful environment and lasted approximately 20 to 30 minutes. After the interviews, the researchers proceeded to the coding stage, carefully reviewing and analyzing the transcribed data. Through this process, various significant statements and ideas were identified, allowing different themes to emerge.

Ethical Consideration This study adhered to strict ethical considerations to ensure research integrity and participant safety. Participants were fully informed about the study's purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits before data collection, and informed consent was obtained through signed consent forms. Participation was voluntary, with the option to withdraw at any time without penalty. The research methods were reviewed and approved by the adviser and the institution's ethics review board. Confidentiality and anonymity were rigorously maintained, and all personal data were handled securely in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, used exclusively for academic purposes.

Research Reflexivity According to McLeod (2024), reflexivity in research includes the researcher's ongoing self-awareness and critical self-reflection regarding their own personal biases, prejudices, and relationship to the study. This process enables the identification and reduction of personal bias influence on the research.

Over the course of the study, the researchers have learned a lot about how power naps could affect college students' motivation in their studies. After conducting semi-structured interviews with the participants and examining their experiences, the researchers have realized how academic pressure and academic demands became a strong factor on why a lot of students ignore power napping or taking a rest leading to physical and emotional exhaustion and declining motivation. The researchers now concluded that many college students including them are caught in a vicious cycle of overworking themselves to the point where they must sacrifice sleep in order to meet academic obligations.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two primary themes emerged from the thematic analysis, encapsulating the challenges, and coping strategies related to college students' power napping. These themes authentically reflect the lived experiences of the participants. To underscore the depth and credibility of their accounts, direct quotations from the participants have been incorporated, providing vivid insights into each identified issue.

Table 1: Thematic Map

1. Power Nap as Source of Rejuvenation

This theme aligns with the concept of Slow-Wave Sleep (SWS), the deepest stage of non-REM sleep. According to the research of Ambrosini and Giuditta (2001), SWS removes non-adaptive memory traces in the brain and promotes the transfer of information from short-term to long-term memory. Meanwhile, the Restorative Theory of Sleep emphasizes that sleep is essential for restoring the body and brain to optimal functioning. Deep sleep phases like the SWS are crucial for body tissue regeneration, energy conservation, and promoting overall physical and mental well-being.

Although SWS usually happens during longer sleep cycles, even quick power naps can incorporate non-REM sleep that could help support mental recovery and memory processing. Several participants emphasized that power naps made them feel more rested and productive. **Participant 3** expressed, "**Maturog kadali tapos magwork utro kay narefresh a mind**" ("Sleep for a little while, then work again since the mind feels renewed").

In the case of **Participant 1**, she said that sleeping helped reduce her fatigue, stating, "**Makabulig ini sa iba labi na kun fatigue gud**" ("This might benefit others, especially when they're feeling weary"). Similarly, Participant 6 expressed that power naps provide her with the energy she needed to meet her deadlines. These are testimonies that demonstrate how college students see power naps as a useful and efficient way to deal with fatigue and keep up their academic work.

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2. Enduring Academic Exhaustion

This theme highlights how the participants struggle with physical and mental exhaustion, often resisting the urge to rest and ultimately normalizing tiredness as part of their daily routine. From the perspective of Self-Determination Theory (SDT), this behaviour may be interpreted as a reflection of students' internal conflicts between autonomy and external pressures. Evidence shows that short rest periods can be beneficial. A short nap of just 20 minutes has been found to reduce sleepiness and improve mood, alertness, reaction time, short-term memory, and overall concentration (Clinic, 2021).

Despite the proven benefits of short rest, many college students remain overwhelmed by deadlines, academic pressure, and exams—factors that often disrupt healthy sleep patterns. Participant 7 shared that during deadlines, they resort to cramming: “**Cramming labi na kun due date asya ginpush it sarili na dire maturog**” (“Cramming, especially when it’s the due date, that’s when I push myself not to sleep”), reflecting the intense workload that leaves little opportunity for recovery.

2.1 Mental and Physical Exhaustion

Majority of the participants expressed that the heavy academic workload left them with little time for rest. **Participant 2** said that “**Damo it hirimuon so nawawaray time pagrest**” (“There’s so much to do that there’s no time to rest”) indicating how busy schedules prevent students from prioritizing rest. For Participant 8, she said that she feels tired even though it is just 10 am in the morning reflecting how fatigue sets in even early in the day due to lack of sleep or rest. Consequently, many participants reported experiencing persistent physical and mental exhaustion, which made it difficult to remain focused and productive in their academic tasks.

This finding aligns with the study of Jaizul et al. (2025) study which revealed that students' GPA and academic performance are adversely affected by inconsistent sleep habits. These results demonstrate how irregular sleep patterns impact students' everyday energy levels and have great implications for their academic performance. Students' cognitive ability tends to deteriorate when they are mentally tired, which frequently leads to mental blocks and difficulty processing information.

2.2 Self-Control Against Napping

In a research by Sethy (2024), naps can enhance mood, reduce irritability, and promote emotional balance, all of which contribute to mental health in general. However, some students admitted to intentionally resisting the urge to nap by self-regulating through physical means. Many college students use various techniques to control their drowsiness. Example is **Participant 5**, who would physically inflict pain on himself to stay awake. He said, “**Abutting hin maharang ha mata, ginkukutol ko gihap tak sarili para dre mangaturog.**” (“I put something over my eyes and would pinch myself to avoid falling asleep.”) On the other hand, Participant 4 engages in callisthenics to keep him awake. Despite these control strategies, participants said that deliberately pushing themselves to continue working despite exhaustion makes them drained afterwards, leading them no energy to do more work

2.2 Settling into Fatigue

Fatigue due to lack of sleep is a common experience among college students. Some respondents shared that they have become accustomed to their demanding schedules. One stated, “**Nahiara nala na sugad it sitwasyun,**” (“I got accustomed to the situation”) suggesting a normalization of overwork and lack of sleep. Interestingly, the study of Walker and Stickgold (2010) argued that REM sleep plays an integrative role by forming links between new information and existing knowledge. This

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underscores the cognitive cost of chronic sleep deprivation—by depriving themselves of adequate sleep, students may have undermined their ability to synthesize and apply what they learned in school.

Despite being aware of the importance of rest, students often chose to sacrifice sleep to keep up with deadlines and responsibilities. This habitual exhaustion became a routine among students and becomes a part of their college life, where feeling tired was no longer seen as unusual, but rather expected. Participants who did not engage in power naps were aware of their potential benefits; however, they perceived napping as a waste of time and feared oversleeping.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The findings indicate that power naps serve as both a physiological and strategic resource, enhancing students' academic performance as well as their physical and mental well-being. They provide a cost-effective and efficient way for students—particularly those balancing academic responsibilities with personal commitments—to obtain restorative rest. Based on these results, it is recommended that educational administrations and student affairs offices consider implementing flexible scheduling policies that allow short breaks during class sessions to facilitate student rest.

Furthermore, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) are encouraged to establish designated “Power Nap Corners” on campus by utilizing underused spaces such as classrooms, libraries, or lounges to provide clean, quiet, and restful environments for students. In addition, institutions should collaborate with experts in sleep science, healthcare, and mental health to conduct seminars and workshops aimed at raising awareness of healthy sleep practices.

References

- Ambrosini, Maria Vittoria & Giuditta, A. (2001). **Learning and sleep: The sequential hypothesis. *Sleep medicine reviews***. 5. 477-490. [10.1053/smrv.2001.0180](https://doi.org/10.1053/smrv.2001.0180). .
- Carley, D. W., & Farabi, S. S. (2016). **Physiology of sleep. *Diabetes Spectrum***, 29(1), 5–9. <https://doi.org/10.2337/diaspect.29.1.5>
- Cleveland Clinic. **Sleep**. (2023). <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/body/12148-sleep-basics>
- Clinic, C. (2021, November 11). **Power naps: Benefits and how to do it. *Cleveland Clinic***. <https://health.clevelandclinic.org/power-naps>
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). **Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches** (3rd ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Crivello, A., Barsocchi, P., & Girolami, M. (2019). **The meaning of sleep quality: A survey of available technologies. *IEEE Access***. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2953835>
- George, A. S., George, A. S., & Shahul, A. (2024). **The science and timing of power naps: Investigating the cognitive and physical benefits of brief daytime sleep. *02***, 70–84. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10673171>

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- Hershner, S. D., & Chervin, R. D. (2014). **Causes and consequences of sleepiness among college students.** *Nature and Science of Sleep*, 6, 73–84. <https://doi.org/10.2147/NSS.S62907>
- Jaizul, A., & Vera. (2025). **Literature review: The relationship between irregular sleep patterns and cognitive decline in college students.** *International Journal of Health, Medicine, and Sports*, 3, 44–48. <https://doi.org/10.46336/ijhms.v3i2.215>
- McLeod, S. (2024). **Reflexivity in qualitative research.** Simply Psychology. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/reflexivity-in-qualitative-research.html>
- Okano, K., Kaczmarzyk, J. R., Dave, N., Gabrieli, J. D. E., & Grossman, J. C. (2019). **Sleep quality, duration, and consistency are associated with better academic performance in college students.** *NPJ Science of Learning*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41539-019-0055-z>
- Pilcher, J. J., & Walters, A. S. (1997). **How sleep deprivation affects psychological variables related to college students' cognitive performance.** *Journal of American College Health*, 46(3), 121–126. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07448489709595597>
- Schlarb, A. A., Friedrich, A., & Claßen, M. (2017). **Sleep problems in university students – an intervention.** *Neuropsychiatric Disease and Treatment*, 13, 1989–2001.
- Sethy, A. (2024). **Why power naps are good for brain health and productivity.** *HealthSpectra*. <https://www.healthspectra.com/why-power-naps-are-good-for-brain-health-and-productivity/>
- Summer, J. V., & Summer, J. V. (2023). **Power Nap.** *Sleep Foundation*. <https://www.sleepfoundation.org/sleep-hygiene/power-nap>
- Walker, M. P., & Stickgold, R. (2010). **Overnight alchemy: Sleep-dependent memory evolution.** *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 11(3), 218. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn2762-c1>

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